

Tailoring perovskite surface composition to design efficient lean NO_x trap Pd–La_{1-x}A_xCoO₃/Al₂O₃-type catalysts (with A = Sr or Ba)

Jon A. Onrubia-Calvo^a, Beñat Pereda-Ayo^a, Angel Caravaca^b, Unai De-La-Torre^a, Philippe Vernoux^b and Juan R. González-Velasco^{a,}*

^a Departamento de Ingeniería Química, Facultad de Ciencia y Tecnología, Universidad del País Vasco, UPV/EHU, Campus de Leioa, P. O. Box 644, ES-48080 Bilbao, Bizkaia, Spain

^b Université de Lyon, Institut de Recherches sur la Catalyse et l'Environnement de Lyon, UMR 5256, CNRS, Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, 2 avenue A. Einstein, F-69626 Villeurbanne, France

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*Corresponding author: juanra.gonzalezvelasco@ehu.eus

ABSTRACT

1 Here we report the influence of surface composition on the NO_x removal efficiency of lean NO_x
2 trap Pd–La_{1-x}A_xCoO₃/Al₂O₃-type catalysts. Three catalysts were prepared by the sequential
3 impregnation of 30 wt.% of La_{1-x}A_xCoO₃-type perovskites and 1.9 wt.% of Pd over alumina.
4 The following perovskite compositions were used: La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃, La_{0.7}Ba_{0.3}CoO₃ or
5 La_{0.5}Ba_{0.5}CoO₃. The results of X-Ray diffraction, N₂ adsorption-desorption at –196 °C, electron
6 microscopy, temperature programmed techniques, and Raman and X-ray photoelectron
7 spectroscopies demonstrated that lanthanum partial substitution by barium promoted the
8 presence of Ba-based phases homogeneously distributed at the surface. This fact together with
9 the higher basicity of Ba than Sr led to an increase of the surface basicity for Ba-doped samples.
10 Likewise, Ba doping also favors the formation of small PdO particles homogeneously distributed
11 over the surface in close contact with the perovskite phase. Hence, the interactions between Pd
12 and surface basic sites were also promoted. As a result, 1.9 wt.% Pd–
13 30 wt.% La_{0.5}Ba_{0.5}CoO₃/Al₂O₃ catalyst exhibited the highest NO_x adsorption and reduction
14 efficiency. Specifically, the NO global conversion and nitrogen production were as high as 90%
15 and 72% at 350 °C, respectively. The enhancement of NO_x storage capacity during the lean
16 period is mainly assigned to the displacement of gas/solid equilibrium between NO₂ and the
17 available NO_x adsorption sites due to the presence of higher concentration of basic sites at the
18 surface. Meanwhile, the promotion of the NO_x reduction capacity is due to the higher strength
19 of NO_x adsorbed species, which slows down the decomposition rate of NO_x adsorbed species.
20 Furthermore, the high proximity of Pd and perovskite phase favors the intermediate compounds
21 diffusion. These results confirmed the excellent NO_x removal efficiency of the
22 30 wt.% La_{0.5}Ba_{0.5}CoO₃-based catalyst, even above than Pt-based model catalyst.

24 1. INTRODUCTION

25 Lean-burn combustion engines are attractive because they allow saving more than 20% of fuel
26 and simultaneously limiting CO₂ emissions. However, the operation in a net oxidizing
27 environment makes the reduction of the produced nitrogen oxides (NO_x) much more difficult. In
28 fact, traditional three-way catalysts (TWCs) are not sufficiently efficient under these conditions
29 [1]. To meet stringent standard regulations of NO_x emissions (EURO 6), several alternatives
30 have been explored. Among them, NO_x storage and reduction (NSR) and selective catalytic
31 reduction (SCR), as well as the combined NSR–SCR system have been considered as the most
32 promising approaches [2]. NSR technology, also known as lean NO_x trap system (LNT),
33 operates under cycling conditions with a 1–2% Pt/10–15% BaO/Al₂O₃ model catalyst [3].
34 During the lean period, NO is oxidized into NO₂ on Pt sites, which is then stored on barium sites
35 in the form of nitrites or nitrates. In the subsequent rich period, the environment switches to
36 reducing conditions by the injection of a reductant such as H₂, CO or HC. As a result, the stored
37 nitrites/nitrates are released and reduced preferentially to N₂ over Pt sites [4].

38 Current NSR catalysts contain a considerable amount of noble metals such as Pt or Pt–Rh (1–2
39 wt.%), which increases the catalyst cost in an important manner [5]. To save the limited
40 resources of noble metals and decrease the catalyst cost, perovskite-based catalysts have been
41 proposed to replace the noble metals, especially in oxidation processes [6]. Our previous work
42 demonstrated that Co-based perovskites are the most promising noble-metal-free catalysts for
43 NO oxidation in automobile application, even exhibiting better catalytic performance than NSR
44 model catalysts [7]. However, these formulations were prepared by calcination at high
45 temperature (above 650 °C). This led to very low specific surface areas (below 20 m² g⁻¹),
46 which decreased the amount of active sites available for the catalytic reactions. As a result, high
47 NO_x removal efficiencies in the NO_x storage/reduction process were hard to achieve. The
48 impregnation of 30% of La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃ perovskite over γ–Al₂O₃ has proven to be a promising
49 alternative to overcome this limitation. The higher NO_x removal efficiency of alumina-
50 supported perovskite was mainly ascribed to easier diffusion of intermediate compounds from
51 oxidation sites to adsorption sites [8]. NO_x reduction capacity was further promoted by the
52 impregnation of small amounts of Pd over 30% La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃/Al₂O₃ catalyst, with the
53 1.5% Pd–30% La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃/Al₂O₃ catalyst as the optimum formulation [9]. Palladium was
54 selected due to the higher thermal stability than Pt in NSR systems, high activity for CO and
55 hydrocarbons oxidation and its positive effect in improving the sulphur tolerance of the catalyst
56 [10–13].

57 However, a high NO₂ concentration was observed in the aforementioned study under oxidizing
58 conditions. It suggests that the amount of NO₂ produced on these materials is higher than the

59 amount that can be adsorbed during the lean period [13, 14]. Furthermore, we observed a
60 significant amount of NO_x released during rich conditions, which denotes a low stability of NO_x
61 adsorbed species. This fact partially limits the reduction of NO_x adsorbed species during the rich
62 period. Hence, increasing the concentration and strength of NO_x adsorption sites could be an
63 efficient alternative to overcome these limitations. As observed in our previous work [7], the
64 variation of perovskite formulation strongly affects the surface composition. As a result, this
65 alternative emerges as a simple way to modify the NO₂-to-NO_x adsorption sites equilibrium
66 and NO_x adsorbed species decomposition rate [15-17]. Ba is the typical NO_x adsorption site in
67 the NO_x storage and reduction model catalyst (1.5% Pt–15% BaO/Al₂O₃). Furthermore, Hodjati
68 et al. [18] analyzed the NO_x storage performance of ABO₃ perovskite-type catalysts (with A =
69 Ca, Sr or Ba; and B = Sn, Zr or Ti). Regarding A-site cations, the NO_x storage capacity (NSC)
70 was in the order of Ba > Sr > Ca. Hence, the partial substitution of La³⁺ by Ba²⁺ seems to be a
71 promising alternative to promote the overall NO_x storage and reduction activity of Pd–
72 30% La_{1-x}ACoO₃/Al₂O₃-type catalysts.

73 Thus, the main objective of this study is to tailor the perovskite formulation to maximize the
74 NO_x removal by the NO_x storage and reduction process. Therefore, in the present work, a series
75 of perovskite-based formulations were prepared by the sequential impregnation of 30 wt.%
76 perovskite and 1.9 wt.% of Pd over an alumina support. The catalyst with optimum perovskite
77 compositions according to our previous work (La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃ formulation) [7] was compared to
78 a new series of catalysts based on the following Ba-doped perovskites: La_{0.7}Ba_{0.3}CoO₃ and
79 La_{0.5}Ba_{0.5}CoO₃. The prepared samples were thoroughly characterized and tested for the NO_x
80 storage and reduction process, paying special attention to the identification of the nature,
81 strength and concentration of the different NO_x adsorption sites.

82 2. EXPERIMENTAL

83 **2.1. Perovskite-based samples preparation.** 1.9% Pd–30% La_{1-x}A_xBO₃/Al₂O₃-type
84 catalysts were prepared by sequential impregnation of different perovskite formulations
85 (La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃, La_{0.7}Ba_{0.3}CoO₃ or La_{0.5}Ba_{0.5}CoO₃) and Pd as reported in our previous work [8].
86 Firstly, stoichiometric amounts of La(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (*Fluka*, 99%), Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (*Sigma*
87 *Aldrich*, 98%) and Sr(NO₃)₂ (*Sigma Aldrich*, 99%) or Ba(NO₃)₂ (*Sigma Aldrich*, 99%) were
88 dissolved in distilled water under vigorous stirring. Then, citric acid (C₆H₈O₇·H₂O, *Sigma*
89 *Aldrich*, 99%) was added as a complexing agent with a citrate to nitrate molar ratio of 1.1. The
90 pH value was adjusted by ammonia water (25% as NH₃, *Panreac*) to a value of 8. The resulting
91 solution was added to the alumina (previously calcined at 700 °C for 4 h in static air) inside a
92 rotary evaporator (vacuum and 35 °C) to obtain a homogeneously distributed gel precursor over
93 the alumina. After solvent evaporation at 80 °C, the gel was further dried at 120 °C overnight

94 and then calcined at 650 °C for 4 h under a flow of 5% O₂/He to get the desired alumina-
95 supported perovskite. The following samples were synthesized: 30% La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃/Al₂O₃
96 (LSCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃), 30% La_{0.7}Ba_{0.3}CoO₃/Al₂O₃ (LBCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃) and
97 30% La_{0.5}Ba_{0.5}CoO₃/Al₂O₃ (LBCO(0.5)/Al₂O₃). Finally, 1.9 wt.% of Pd was incorporated by
98 wetness impregnation. Tetraamminepalladium (II) nitrate solution was used as precursor,
99 [Pd(NH₃)₄(NO₃)₂]. The resulting samples were calcined at 500 °C for 4 h in static air. The
100 adopted nomenclature for the fully formulated samples was the following: Pd-
101 LSCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃, Pd-LBCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ and Pd-LBCO(0.5)/Al₂O₃.

102 **2.2. Catalysts characterization.** XRD diffractions patterns of the samples were obtained on a
103 Philips PW1710 diffractometer. The samples were finely ground and subjected to Cu K_α
104 radiation in a continuous scan mode from 5° to 70° 2θ with 0.02° per second sampling interval.
105 PANalytical X`pert HighScore specific software was used for data treatment.

106 Raman spectroscopy was performed at room temperature in the regions of 250–750 cm⁻¹ or
107 850–1350 cm⁻¹ using a LabRam HR (Horiba) spectrometer equipped with a CCD detector
108 cooled at -75 °C. Measurements were carried out under microscope with a laser wavelength of
109 514.53 nm. A low dispersion grating of 1800 grooves/mm was chosen to get a maximum signal
110 (to improve the resolution). The spectra were recorded and treated using the Labspec software
111 (Horiba). Prior to the analysis, the instrument was calibrated using a silicon wafer. Six Raman
112 mappings of 25 analysis points were systematically carried out with a motorized plate to control
113 the homogeneity and purity of the prepared catalysts.

114 An Environmental Transmission Electron Microscope (ETEM) was used to visualize the nano-
115 structure of the selected catalysts after reduction at 250 °C for 1 h. This latest generation ETEM
116 (Titan 80–300 kV from FEI™) was equipped with an imaging aberration corrector and an
117 energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) analyzer (SDD X-Max 80 mm² from Oxford Instruments™)
118 used for elemental chemical analysis. The sample was deposited on titania grids covered with a
119 silica film and placed into a Gatan™ furnace-type holder.

120 Textural properties of the samples were determined by N₂ adsorption-desorption at -196 °C,
121 using a Micromeritics TriStar equipment.

122 Pd, La, Sr, Al₂O₃ and Co loadings were quantitatively determined by Inductively Coupled
123 Plasma Optical Emission Spectroscopy, ICP–OES using a Horiba Jobin Yvon Activa
124 spectrometer. Prior to the analysis the samples were pre-reduced at 250 °C for 1 h.

125 The palladium dispersion was determined using the H₂ chemisorption method in a
126 Micromeritics ASAP 2020 equipment. The catalyst (0.2 g) was first outgassed at 30, 110 and

127 350 °C (3 h). Then, the sample was pre-reduced in 50 mL min⁻¹ of 5% H₂/Ar at 110 and 350 °C.
128 After that, the sample was further outgassed at 350 °C to remove the residual hydrogen. Finally,
129 H₂ was dosed isothermally (70 °C) and the volume adsorbed was recorded. Before repeating
130 this path the sample was again outgassed for 60 min, the difference between both isotherms was
131 related with H₂ chemisorbed on the catalyst surface.

132 Pd oxidation states and surface content was analyzed using X-ray photoelectronic spectroscopy
133 (XPS). The analysis were carried out in a SPECS electron spectrometer with a Phoibos 150 1D-
134 DLD energy analyzer using Al-K α (1486.7 eV) radiation source. To obtain the XPS spectra, the
135 pressure of the analysis chamber was maintained at 5×10^{-10} mbar. The binding energy (BE)
136 scale was adjusted by setting the C 1s transition at 284.6 eV.

137 The reducibility of the samples was investigated via Temperature Programmed Reduction
138 experiments (TPR) using the Micromeritics AutoChem II equipment. The quartz tube reactor
139 was loaded with 0.1 g of sample and pretreated in 30 mL min⁻¹ of 5% O₂/He mixture at 600 °C
140 for 30 min and then cooled down to -10 °C. Then, samples were heated from -10 °C to 950 °C
141 at 10 °C min⁻¹ in a 5% H₂/Ar mixture (30 mL min⁻¹). Water generated during the reduction was
142 trapped by a cold trap. The gas stream was then analyzed by a TCD detector.

143 The surface basicity of the samples was investigated using the Micromeritics AutoChem II
144 equipment coupled to a MKS Cirrus LM99 mass spectrometer. The quartz tube reactor was
145 loaded with 0.1 g of sample and pretreated in 50 mL min⁻¹ of 5% O₂/He mixture at 550 °C for
146 30 min and then cooled down to 35 °C in a flow of He. The adsorption of CO₂ was performed in
147 a flow of 5% CO₂/He (50 mL min⁻¹) for 60 min. Then, samples were heated from room
148 temperature to 900 °C with a temperature ramp of 10 °C min⁻¹ in He (50 mL min⁻¹). The CO₂
149 desorption was continuously monitored with a mass spectrometer following the CO₂ signal
150 (m/e=44).

151 For the NO adsorption/desorption experiments, a quartz tube reactor was loaded with 0.1 g of
152 sample and pretreated in 20% O₂/He (170 mL min⁻¹) at 500 °C for 60 min and then cooled down
153 to 350 °C. After that, NO adsorption was performed by feeding a mixture of 500 ppm of NO,
154 6% of O₂ and He (170 mL min⁻¹) until catalyst saturation was achieved. Then, the sample was
155 cooled down to 30 °C with the same gas mixture. Finally, the sample was heated from 30 °C to
156 600 °C at 10 °C min⁻¹ in He (170 mL min⁻¹). The outlet gas concentrations during the desorption
157 process were followed by using an IR online (NGA 2000, for NO and NO₂) and a micro-gas
158 chromatograph (μ GC-R3000, SRA, equipped with a molecular sieved column for O₂ analysis)
159 analyzers in series.

160 **2.3 Catalytic activity**

161 The catalytic tests were carried out with a total flow rate of 2 L min^{-1} (GHSV=123,500 h^{-1}) and
162 catalyst grain size of 0.3–0.5 mm. These experimental conditions guaranteed the absence of
163 external and internal mass transfer limitations [7]. Prior to the activity tests, the catalysts were
164 pre-activated/stabilized at $450 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h under NO_x storage and reduction cycles.

165 The outlet gas composition was continuously measured using a MKS MultiGas 2030 FT-IR
166 analyzer followed by a MKS Cirrus quadrupole MS on line. NO, NO_2 , NH_3 , N_2O and H_2O were
167 quantitatively monitored by the FT-IR analyzer, whereas H_2 , N_2 and O_2 were qualitatively
168 monitored by the MS analyzer.

169 *2.4.1. NO-to- NO_2 oxidation activity.* NO oxidation tests were carried out in a vertical stainless
170 steel reactor filled with 0.5 grams of catalyst inside a 3-zone tube furnace. The feed stream
171 composition was: 500 ppm NO, 6% O_2 and Ar as the balance gas. The NO-to- NO_2 conversion
172 was determined by Equation 1, once the steady state at each temperature was achieved (~ 20
173 mins after the temperature was stabilized).

$$174 \quad X_{\text{NO-to-NO}_2} (\%) = \frac{F_{\text{NO}}^{\text{in}} - F_{\text{NO}}^{\text{out}}}{F_{\text{NO}}^{\text{in}}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

175 where $F_{\text{NO}}^{\text{in}}$ is the NO molar flow ($\mu\text{mol min}^{-1}$) at the inlet, $F_{\text{NO}}^{\text{out}}$ is the NO molar flow
176 ($\mu\text{mol min}^{-1}$) at the outlet at steady state.

177 *2.4.2. NO_x storage and reduction (NSR) experiments.* The reaction system was the same than
178 that for NO oxidation experiments. During the lean period (150 s), the feed composition was:
179 500 ppm NO, 6% O_2 and Ar as the carrier gas. During the rich period (20 s), oxygen was
180 replaced by hydrogen with a concentration of 3%. Gases were fed via mass flow controllers.
181 Temperature was continuously monitored by a thermocouple inside the catalytic bed. The
182 catalytic activity was evaluated in terms of the parameters listed below.

183 *NO_x storage capacity (NSC):* percentage amount of NO_x stored during the lean period related to
184 the amount of NO at the inlet (Equation 2),

$$185 \quad \text{NSC} (\%) = \frac{F_{\text{NO}}^{\text{in}} t_L - \int_0^{t_L} F_{\text{NO}_x}^{\text{out}} dt}{F_{\text{NO}}^{\text{in}} t_L} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

186 $F_{\text{NO}_x}^{\text{out}}$ is the NO_x molar flow ($\mu\text{mol min}^{-1}$) at the outlet and t_L (min) is the length of the lean cycle.

187 *NO global conversion (X_{NO}):* amount of NO converted during the whole operation (lean and
188 rich cycles) with respect to the total amount of NO fed to the reactor (Equation 3),

189
$$X_{NO}(\%) = \frac{F_{NO}^{in}(t_L+t_R) - \int_0^{t_L+t_R} F_{NO}^{out} dt}{F_{NO}^{in}(t_L+t_R)} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

190 where t_R (min) is the length of the rich cycle.

191 NO_x conversion during rich period ($X_{NO_x R}$): amount of NO_x converted during rich period with
 192 respect to the total amount of NO fed to the reactor (Equation 4),

193
$$X_{NO_x R}(\%) = \frac{[F_{NO}^{in} t_L - \int_0^{t_L} F_{NO_x}^{out} dt + F_{NO}^{in} t_R] - \int_{t_L}^{t_L+t_R} F_{NO_x}^{out} dt}{[F_{NO}^{in} t_L - \int_0^{t_L} F_{NO_x}^{out} dt + F_{NO}^{in} t_R]} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

194 *Yield of N-compounds* (Y_{NO_2} , Y_{NH_3} , Y_{N_2O} and Y_{N_2}): mol percentage of the corresponding
 195 component at the outlet related to NO amount at the inlet, i.e.

196
$$Y_{NO_2}(\%) = \frac{\int_0^{t_L+t_R} F_{NO_2}^{out} dt}{F_{NO}^{in}(t_L+t_R)} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

197
$$Y_{NH_3}(\%) = \frac{\int_0^{t_L+t_R} F_{NH_3}^{out} dt}{F_{NO}^{in}(t_L+t_R)} \times 100 \quad (6)$$

198
$$Y_{N_2O}(\%) = \frac{\int_0^{t_L+t_R} 2F_{N_2O}^{out} dt}{F_{NO}^{in}(t_L+t_R)} \times 100 \quad (7)$$

199
$$Y_{N_2}(\%) = \frac{\int_0^{t_L+t_R} 2F_{N_2}^{out} dt}{F_{NO}^{in}(t_L+t_R)} \times 100 \quad (8)$$

200 where $F_{NO_2}^{out}$, $F_{NH_3}^{out}$, $F_{N_2O}^{out}$ and $F_{N_2}^{out}$ are the molar flows ($\mu\text{mol min}^{-1}$) at the outlet of NO_2 , NH_3 ,
 201 N_2O and N_2 , respectively.

202 3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

203 3.1. Catalysts characterization

204 *Phases identification, distribution and morphology.* Figure 1 shows the XRD patterns of the
 205 synthesized catalysts. Diffractograms of $LaCoO_3$ (LSCO(0)), $La_{0.5}Ba_{0.5}CoO_3$ (LBCO(0.5)) and
 206 $La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO_3$ (LSCO(0.3)) bulk perovskites and alumina support (Al_2O_3) are also included as
 207 reference. All the alumina-supported perovskites present the characteristic diffraction peaks of a
 208 highly disordered cubic alumina with low crystallinity (\clubsuit) together with highly crystallized
 209 perovskite. The relative intensity of the perovskite phase characteristic diffraction peaks clearly
 210 decreases with respect to that of their corresponding bulk counterparts. As already reported in
 211 our previous works [8, 9], the perovskite agglomeration during the calcination step is partially

212 inhibited due to its distribution over the alumina surface. As a result, the perovskite crystal size
213 of alumina-supported variants ($d_c=13-16$ nm), determined by Scherrer equation (Table 1), was
214 smaller than that for the bulk counterparts ($d_c=18-21$ nm).

215

FIGURE 1

216 Besides the alumina and perovskite peaks, phase segregations in form of orthorhombic BaCO_3
217 (\bullet), $\text{BaCoO}_{2.95}$ (\blacklozenge) or SrCO_3 (\blacktriangle) were also identified for the fully formulated samples.
218 However, the amount of impurities seems to be higher for Ba-doped samples (BaCO_3 and
219 $\text{BaCoO}_{2.95}$). This suggests that Sr^{2+} accommodation within the lattice may be higher than that for
220 Ba^{2+} . It could be attributed, on the one hand, to the higher basicity of Ba compared to Sr, which
221 favors the carbonation of segregated barium oxides [19, 20]. On the other hand, the ionic radius
222 of La^{3+} (1.15 Å) is closer to that of Sr^{2+} (1.13 Å) than Ba^{2+} (1.35 Å) leading to a displacement of
223 the main perovskite peak position to lower values for Ba-doped samples due to the increase in
224 the interplanar distances of the perovskite crystals (Figure 1b). As a result, it limits the fraction
225 of Ba^{2+} that can be accommodated in the structure without the formation of additional phases,
226 such as $\text{BaCoO}_{2.95}$ perovskite [21]. The comparison of the relative peak intensity for perovskite
227 and additional phases in samples with different barium doping degree seems to indicate that the
228 formation of additional phases is higher as the amount of Ba^{2+} increased. Finally, Pd or PdO
229 peaks were absent for the fully formulated samples due to small particle size and/or low content
230 [22].

231 Figure 2 shows Raman spectra for Pd-LSCO(0.3)/ Al_2O_3 , Pd-LBCO(0.3)/ Al_2O_3 and Pd-
232 LBCO(0.5)/ Al_2O_3 samples. In order to made the assignment of different Raman lines, Figure S1
233 shows the corresponding Raman spectra for Co_3O_4 , Al_2O_3 , LSCO(0.3), CoAl_2O_4 and Pd/ Al_2O_3
234 reference samples. Based on results of Figure S1a, several bands at 483, 525, 623 and 692 cm^{-1}
235 identified irrespective the perovskite composition are attributed to Co_3O_4 (Figure 2a). The
236 observed relative intensity of the Co_3O_4 bands is slightly higher for Pd-LBCO(0.5)/ Al_2O_3
237 sample. On the other hand, PdO phase shows a single Raman line located at 646 cm^{-1} (Figure
238 S1e), which is attributed to the Raman active B_{1g} vibration mode of PdO [23, 24]. Finally, the
239 absence of Raman bands for the $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{CoO}_3$ perovskite (Figure S1c) may be due to the small
240 penetration depth of the excitation radiation [25, 26].

241

FIGURE 2

242 Information about the different carbonated phases was obtained by the analysis of the specific
243 zone from 850 to 1350 cm^{-1} (Figure 2b). The bands centered at 1070 cm^{-1} and 1057 cm^{-1} are
244 assigned to SrCO_3 and BaCO_3 phases, respectively [27, 28]. Two trends can be identified in this
245 case. On the one hand, the relative intensity of the main band of SrCO_3 phase is higher than that

246 for BaCO₃ phase in the samples with the same Ba²⁺ and Sr²⁺ molar composition (Pd–
247 LSCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ and Pd–LBCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃). On the other hand, increasing the barium doping
248 degree (Pd–LBCO(0.5)/Al₂O₃) also leads to an increase of the relative intensity of the carbonate
249 band, which could be attributed to a higher amount of segregations, as previously observed by
250 XRD analysis. Both trends are assigned to an increase of crystal domain of the corresponding
251 phases.

252 The control of the homogeneity and distribution of Co₃O₄, BaCO₃ or SrCO₃ and PdO phases in
253 the fully formulated samples is crucial, considering that these species have a significant impact
254 on NO oxidation, NO_x adsorption and their subsequent reduction, respectively. The structural
255 and chemical homogeneity was studied by analyzing an area of ~ 25 × 25 μm for both, Pd–
256 LSCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ and Pd–LBCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ samples by Raman spectroscopy. Figure S2
257 illustrates the representation of the 30 spectra made in the area of 25 × 25 μm for Pd–
258 LSCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ catalyst as reference.

259 Figure 3 shows the spatial distribution of Co₃O₄, PdO, and BaCO₃ or SrCO₃ phases based on
260 their respective Raman band intensities for Pd–LSCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ and Pd–LBCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃
261 samples. Co₃O₄ traces are identified in both samples. However, the average intensity of the main
262 band at 690 cm⁻¹ is weaker for Pd–LBCO (0.3)/Al₂O₃, which denotes smaller crystal domains.
263 Additionally, the spatial distribution of Co₃O₄ spinel seems to be more homogenous for the Pd–
264 LBCO (0.3)/Al₂O₃ sample. Similarly, PdO phase (646 cm⁻¹) shows relative lower intensity as
265 well as more homogeneous distribution for Pd–LBCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃. Taking into account that the
266 main Raman line of PdO phase was almost negligible for Pd–LBCO(0.5)/Al₂O₃ sample in Figure
267 2, we can suggest that Ba-doping favors the generation of PdO nanoparticles with smaller
268 crystal domain. Regarding SrCO₃ (1070 cm⁻¹) and BaCO₃ (1057 cm⁻¹), in agreement with the
269 observed for PdO and Co₃O₄ phases, Pd–LBCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ seems to exhibit higher structural
270 and chemical homogeneity as a consequence of smaller crystal domains and higher distribution
271 degree of BaCO₃ phase. Overall, these results seem to indicate that the Ba-doped sample shows
272 a more homogeneous distribution of the different phases with respect to the Sr-doped sample.

273

FIGURE 3

274 The distribution of La, Co, Sr, Ba, Al and Pd as well as the morphology of the different phases
275 was studied by TEM/STEM–EDX analysis. Figure 4 shows the STEM images and the
276 corresponding EDX mappings of Al, Pd, La, Co, and Sr or Ba elements for the Pd–
277 LSCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ and Pd–LBCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ catalysts. According to the EDX mapping of Al,
278 La, Co, and Sr or Ba, perovskite phase is distributed over the alumina support, with La, Co, and
279 Sr or Ba homogeneously distributed over the sampled area. However, some areas where the

280 perovskite is concentrated are also observable, evidenced by La, Co, and Sr or Ba rich domains
281 in EDX. This fact is especially remarkable in the case of the Pd–LSCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ sample,
282 which suggests a higher perovskite and SrCO₃ agglomeration for the Sr-doped sample in line
283 with the observed by Raman spectroscopy (Figures 2 and 3).

284 **FIGURE 4**

285 Additional STEM images are shown on Fig. S3. Small spherical Pd particles (~ 3–5 nm)
286 distributed onto alumina and perovskite surface can be observed for both samples. However,
287 according to Figures 4 and S3, Pd distribution seems to be more homogeneous in the Ba-doped
288 perovskite, in good agreement with the above described results obtained by Raman
289 spectroscopy (Fig. 3). In fact, Pd seems to be mainly supported on alumina for Pd–
290 LSCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ sample (Figure 4), whereas this compound is homogeneously distributed on
291 alumina and perovskite surface in the case of Pd–LBCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ sample.

292 *Textural properties.* As a general trend, the N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms of the developed
293 formulations (not shown here) are characteristic of mesoporous materials according to the
294 IUPAC classification. Table 1 summarizes the main textural properties obtained from N₂
295 adsorption-desorption experiments for the synthesized catalysts. The specific surface area (SSA)
296 and pore volume of bare alumina are 186.5 m² g⁻¹ and 0.63 cm³ g⁻¹, respectively. As expected,
297 the specific surface areas (SSA) decrease to values ranging between 119.1–122.7 m² g⁻¹ for the
298 fully formulated samples. In addition, pore volume decreases proportionally to values in the
299 range of 0.37–0.39 cm³ g⁻¹. The decrease of SSA is ascribed to the partial occupation of alumina
300 pores by different perovskite formulations. In any case, the similar SSA values obtained for all
301 samples denote that the perovskite phase agglomeration during calcination is inhibited in a
302 similar extent in all cases.

303 **TABLE 1**

304 *Palladium loading, dispersion and distribution.* Table 2 summarizes Pd weight percents
305 (determined by ICP–OES) and dispersions (estimated by H₂-chemisorption) for fully formulated
306 samples. Furthermore, the Pd main oxidation state and atomic content at the surface (determined
307 from XPS analysis) are also included. Regarding Pd content, the type of the perovskite
308 formulation has no influence over PdO impregnation feasibility, with all the developed
309 formulations showing similar palladium contents (~ 1.9 wt.%). However, Pd dispersion (Pd_{disp.})
310 seems to be slightly affected by the perovskite formulation, in good agreement with the STEM–
311 EDX analysis. Specifically, it ranges from 19.4% for Pd–LSCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ sample to 24.0% for
312 Pd–LBCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ sample. Thus, these results reveal that Pd dispersion was slightly limited
313 for Sr-doped sample.

314

TABLE 2

315 Figure 5 shows the XPS spectra of Pd 3d core level for the catalysts with different perovskite
316 formulations together with Pd/Al₂O₃ reference sample. The oxide character of the Pd particles
317 for all samples was evidenced by the displacement of the BE peaks around 0.6–1.6 eV to higher
318 values with respect to the one reported for metallic state (335.5 eV) [29, 30]. In this sense, the
319 developed formulations show peaks centered around 336.7 ± 0.5 eV, which could be ascribed to
320 the characteristic BE of Pd²⁺ species (336.7 eV) [31]. Furthermore, the high symmetry of Pd
321 3d_{5/2} peak suggests the relatively homogeneous environment of Pd ions. However, the peak
322 position is slightly influenced by the perovskite formulation (Table 2). It is worth noting that the
323 Pd 3d photopeak shifted to higher BE for Pd–LBCO (0.3)/Al₂O₃ (337.1 eV) compared to the
324 Pd–LSCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ (336.2 eV) and Pd/Al₂O₃ samples. These results could be ascribed to the
325 presence of small PdO_x clusters segregated over the surface interacting strongly with the
326 perovskite [32, 33] for Pd–LBCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃, or to the lower electron transfer from PdO to
327 La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃ derived from its more heterogeneous distribution, preferentially over alumina
328 support, which limits Pd-perovskite interactions [34, 35]. These results are in good agreement
329 with the higher Pd dispersion observed for the Pd–LBCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ sample compared to Pd–
330 LSCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ measured by H₂-chemisorption experiments, and the more homogeneous Pd
331 and perovskite distribution observed by Raman spectroscopy (Fig. 3) and STEM imaging (Fig.
332 4).

333

FIGURE 5

334 Finally, Table 2 gives Pd atomic percent estimated from the Pd 3d relative data. As can be
335 observed all samples show similar values. In summary, the observed results show a slightly
336 promotion of palladium dispersion by barium doping.

337 *Palladium-perovskite interactions.* Figure 6 shows the hydrogen consumption profiles
338 normalized per sample mass unit obtained by a Temperature Programmed Reduction (H₂-TPR)
339 experiment. As we previously reported [8, 9], 30% La_{1-x}A_xCoO₃/Al₂O₃-type formulations show
340 two main H₂ consumption regions, i.e. below and above 750 °C. Before Pd incorporation (Fig.
341 6a), H₂ consumption below 750 °C is assigned to the progressive reduction of Co³⁺ to Co⁰ from
342 the surface or near-surface layers [8] which is favored on the supported perovskite materials
343 with respect to the bulk perovskite counterparts (see Figure S4). However, the high distribution
344 of the perovskite phase over alumina also promotes a strong interaction between the Co and
345 alumina in close contact. As a result, a highly stable cobalt aluminate phase (CoAl₂O₄) is
346 formed [8], which is reduced above 750 °C.

347

FIGURE 6

348 As reported in our previous work [9], the reduction of the different species occurs at
349 significantly lower temperatures after the Pd incorporation (Fig. 6b). This is due to the hydrogen
350 dissociation and activation at the surface of the Pd⁰ and its subsequent spillover to Co sites [36,
351 37]. Furthermore, a new contribution ascribed to the reduction of PdO_x species appears below
352 50 °C [38]. Based on the results reported in Figure S4 for Pd/Al₂O₃ reference sample, this peak
353 could be attributed to the reduction of isolated PdO_x clusters over alumina support and as a
354 consequence in weak interaction with the perovskite. It is worth noting that the reducibility and
355 the concentration of the different species are affected by the perovskite composition. Table 3
356 shows the integrated area related to the reduction of the different species. In this sense, the H₂
357 consumption assigned to the reduction of isolated PdO_x particles reduction, decreases from 82
358 μmol H₂ g⁻¹ for Pd–LSCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ sample to values below 13 μmol H₂ g⁻¹ for the Ba-doped
359 formulations. This fact is in good agreement with the lower Pd dispersion, preferential
360 distribution over alumina support and less homogeneous distribution observed for Pd–
361 LSCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ sample by H₂-chemisorption, Raman spectroscopy, STEM imaging and XPS
362 analysis.

363

TABLE 3

364 It is worth to mention that the H₂ consumption ascribed to PdO_x isolated clusters is lower than
365 the nominal value based on the Pd content of the sample measured by ICP analysis (Table 2).
366 Thus, a fraction of Pd should be simultaneously reduced with the perovskite in close contact
367 (50–250 °C). Specifically, the H₂/Pd ratio estimated from the H₂ consumption assigned to the
368 reduction of PdO_x isolated clusters on alumina support decreases from 0.53 for Sr-doped sample
369 to values below 0.09 for Ba-doped samples (Table 3). These results confirm the presence of
370 higher Pd fraction in close contact with the perovskite in the case of Ba-doped samples. As a
371 result, the lowest H₂ consumption centered between 50–250 °C corresponds to Pd–
372 LSCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ (415 μmol H₂ g⁻¹), whereas the highest H₂ consumption corresponds to Pd–
373 LBCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ sample (572 μmol H₂ g⁻¹). Thus, the interaction between PdO phase and
374 perovskite oxide is promoted by Ba doping due to the higher palladium dispersion observed by
375 STEM/TEM images, H₂ chemisorption and Raman experiments.

376 *NO_x adsorption sites distribution and strength.* The surface basicity of the fully formulated
377 samples was analyzed by CO₂-TPD experiments. In order to determine the nature of the
378 different basic sites, Figure 7a shows the CO₂-TPD profiles of Pd–LBCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ samples
379 throughout the different preparation steps.

380 Alumina support shows a single desorption peak centered around 100 °C, which is assigned to
381 the decomposition of bicarbonates formed over OH⁻ ions of alumina [39, 40]. The subsequent

382 incorporation of a 30% of $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Ba}_{0.3}\text{CoO}_3$ perovskite significantly increases the concentration of
383 different basic sites. The promotion of weak (below 200 °C), medium (200–550 °C) and strong
384 basic sites (above 550 °C) is ascribed to the decomposition of monodenate carbonates linked to
385 the perovskite surface, highly dispersed BaCO_3 segregated at the surface and bulk-like BaCO_3
386 with low interaction with the support, respectively [41, 42].

387

FIGURE 7

388 The final incorporation of palladium leads to a small increase of the strong basic peak. This fact
389 is assigned to the partial agglomeration of highly dispersed BaCO_3 during the calcination step
390 after Pd incorporation [43]. It is worth noting that the relative intensity of the BaCO_3
391 characteristic diffraction peaks increased after Pd incorporation in Figure 1 (XRD analysis).

392 Figure 7b shows the corresponding CO_2 -TPD profiles of fully formulated perovskite-based
393 catalysts. As a general trend, two main desorption regions can be observed in all cases, i.e.
394 below and above 550 °C. Table 4 summarizes the concentration of the different species obtained
395 after the integration of the desorption peaks observed in Figure 7b. Pd-LBCO (0.5)/ Al_2O_3
396 shows the highest total surface basicity ($25.5 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ g}^{-1}$). This trend is ascribed to the higher
397 basicity of barium with respect to strontium [2, 44]. Furthermore, the higher concentration of
398 different Ba-based species at the surface also promotes surface basicity [45]. This increase was
399 assigned to the lower Ba^{2+} accommodation degree together with the more homogeneous
400 distribution of BaCO_3 phase as the Ba^{2+} content increased, as previously observed by XRD
401 analysis and Raman spectroscopy. Nevertheless, the highest concentration of strong basic sites
402 (bulk-like carbonates, decomposed at temperatures higher than 550 °C) corresponds to Pd-
403 LSCO(0.3)/ Al_2O_3 due to the partial agglomeration of SrCO_3 phase (Table 4). These results
404 reveal that Sr or Ba doping has significant influence over the surface properties of the catalysts.

405

TABLE 4

406 The nature and the strength of the NO_x adsorbed species was assessed by Temperature
407 Programmed Desorption experiments of NO_x (NO_x -TPD). In this sense, Figure 8 shows the
408 NO_x desorption profiles of Pd-LBCO(0.5)/ Al_2O_3 throughout the different preparation steps.

409

FIGURE 8

410 Alumina support shows a single small desorption peak between 200–300 °C (Figure 8a). As
411 reported in our previous work [8], this could be attributed to the almost negligible NO-to- NO_2
412 oxidation capacity of alumina, which consequently limits its NO_x adsorption capacity. The
413 incorporation of Pd over Al_2O_3 significantly increases the NO_x adsorption/desorption capacity

414 (Figure 8b). This is due to the higher NO oxidation capacity in the presence of Pd, which
415 increases NO₂ concentration, and as a consequence promotes NO_x adsorption in form of nitrates
416 [46, 47]. Two main NO_x desorption regions can be observed for this sample, suggesting the
417 decomposition of NO_x adsorbed species with different stability. The low temperature peak,
418 centered at 159 °C, is assigned to weakly NO_x adsorbed species in form of bridging NO on Pd
419 as well as in form nitrites on alumina surface nearby Pd sites [48, 49]. On the other hand, the
420 high temperature peak, centered at 440 °C could be ascribed to NO_x desorption from bridging
421 bidentate nitrates bounded over alumina surface nearby metal sites [46, 50]. The concomitant
422 desorption of oxygen confirms this assumption. The higher concentration of the first peak
423 species reveals that NO_x is preferentially weakly adsorbed in the Pd/Al₂O₃ sample.

424 The NO_x desorption profile varies in a significant manner for LBCO(0.5)/Al₂O₃ (Figure 8c).
425 One the one hand, the peak centered at 159 °C, identified for Pd/Al₂O₃ sample, disappears due
426 to the absence of Pd as well as alumina surface partial overlap. One the other hand, two new
427 desorption regions were identified, i.e. below and above 300 °C. According to literature, the low
428 temperature peak, centered at 225 °C, could be ascribed to less stable chemisorbed species over
429 Co-sites of the perovskite [51]. Meanwhile, the high temperature region could be assigned to
430 NO_x desorption from basic sites of the perovskite in form of nitrites/nitrates species [42, 52].
431 Two main peaks can be observed in the high temperature region. A NO₂ peak centered at
432 362 °C could be ascribed to the decomposition of adsorbed nitrites/nitrates species over
433 structural La on perovskite surface, while, the peak centered at 430 °C most likely corresponds
434 to decomposition of barium nitrates in form of NO [53, 54]. It is worth noting, as observed in
435 NSR model catalysts, that the NO desorption at high temperatures is accompanied by the
436 evolution of O₂, which confirms the decomposition of NO_x adsorbed species over dispersed
437 barium segregations [42, 55]. Contrary to Pd/Al₂O₃, the high temperature peak is the main one
438 for the LBCO(0.5)/Al₂O₃ sample due to NO_x adsorption via nitrates formation over different
439 BaCO₃ species at the surface. As a result, the NO_x adsorbed species amount and their stability
440 increased with respect to those for Pd/Al₂O₃ (Figure 8b).

441 Finally, the Pd–LBCO(0.5)/Al₂O₃ sample (Figure 8d) exhibits an intermediate profile between
442 Pd/Al₂O₃ (Fig. 8b) and LBCO(0.5)/Al₂O₃ (Fig. 8c) samples. In this case, the low temperature
443 peak decreases with respect to that observed for Pd/Al₂O₃ catalyst, whereas the second one
444 increases with respect to LBCO(0.5)/Al₂O₃ sample. Hence, the coexistence of both Pd and
445 perovskite phases enhanced the formation of NO_x adsorbed species with higher stability and
446 limits NO_x adsorption at low temperature due to alumina partial overlapping by perovskite
447 phase. As a result, the high temperature peak is the main one after Pd and perovskite
448 incorporation.

449 Figure 9 shows the NO_x desorption profiles of the developed catalysts. For all of them, the first
450 peak, centered at ~ 115–130 °C could be ascribed to NO_x desorption due to weakly adsorbed
451 species over palladium surface and alumina support nearby Pd sites, as previously explained.
452 Indeed, the area below this peak follows the same trend than the Pd dispersion (Table 2) on the
453 different catalyst formulations. As a result, the Pd–LBCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ catalyst exhibits the
454 highest concentration of these species. An intermediate temperature contribution, centered at
455 ~ 200–250 °C can be identified, which is ascribed to NO_x desorption from the B-sites of the
456 perovskite (Co) in line with the results above described (Fig. 8). Finally, as previously
457 explained, the high temperature region could be ascribed to NO_x desorption from species
458 formed over structural La on perovskite surface in form of NO₂ (first peak at high temperatures)
459 followed by NO released from barium or strontium nitrates decomposition adsorbed over
460 structural Sr/Ba on perovskite and BaCO₃ or SrCO₃ segregations (highest temperature peak).
461 Hence, the former peak should be proportional to the lanthanum content. As a result, this
462 contribution is lower for Pd–LBCO(0.5)/Al₂O₃, whereas the later is higher for Ba-doped
463 samples due to the higher concentration of Ba-based species at the surface, as previously
464 discussed based on XRD and Raman characterizations. It is worth to mention that the maximum
465 of the high temperature peak shifts to higher temperatures in the case of Pd–LBCO(0.5)/Al₂O₃
466 catalyst (Fig. 9c). Furthermore, this sample also shows the higher amount of NO_x not desorbed
467 at the end of the NO_x–TPD. This trend denotes a higher strength of the NO_x adsorbed species.

468

FIGURE 9

469 The total amount of NO_x desorbed from the fully formulated samples as well as for Pd–
470 LBCO(0.5)/Al₂O₃ throughout the different preparation steps is determined by the integration of
471 NO_x desorption profiles (Figure 10). Among fully formulated catalysts, Pd–LBCO(0.5)/Al₂O₃
472 sample shows the highest concentration of NO_x desorbed species (845.8 μmol NO_x g⁻¹) and Pd–
473 LSCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ the lowest (717.2 μmol NO_x g⁻¹). This fact could be ascribed to the higher
474 NO_x adsorption under oxidizing conditions due to the higher basicity, as determined by CO₂–
475 TPD experiments. However, as observed in Figure 7, the more basic the adsorbent is, the
476 stronger the bonding is to the surface. That is why the NO desorption takes place at higher
477 temperatures for Ba-doped samples.

478

FIGURE 10

479 3.2. Catalytic activity.

480 NO-to-NO₂ conversion ($X_{\text{NO-to-NO}_2}$) was measured at different temperatures (Figure 11) for the
481 developed formulations. The equilibrium conversion for the studied gas stream-feed

482 composition (500 ppm NO, 6% O₂ and Ar to balance) with temperature is also included in
483 broken line as a reference. For all of them, NO oxidation conversion increased with reaction
484 temperature in the kinetically controlled regime up to 350 °C, whereas at higher temperatures
485 the NO-to-NO₂ conversion decreased with temperature due to thermodynamic limitations [12].
486 Perovskite-based formulations show maximum NO-to-NO₂ conversion around 58–65% in all
487 cases. Among them, Pd-LBCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ shows slightly higher NO oxidation capacity. This
488 fact can be ascribed to the more homogeneous distribution of the Co₃O₄ phase observed by
489 Raman spectroscopy.

490

FIGURE 11

491 Figure 12 shows the evolution of the outlet concentration of NO_x, NH₃ and N₂O during two
492 consecutive lean and rich cycles once cycle-to-cycle steady state had been achieved at 350 °C.
493 The MS signal of N₂ is also included. The lowest NO_x outlet concentration is observed at the
494 beginning of the lean period due to NO₂ adsorption over the basic storage components such as
495 SrO, BaO and La₂O₃ of the perovskite [8] and alumina support. After that, the NO_x storage sites
496 of the perovskite became progressively saturated and consequently the NO_x outlet concentration
497 increased gradually. Based on the results reported in Figures 8 and 9, the NO adsorption over
498 these formulations mainly takes places via formation of nitrite (Eq. 9) or nitrate (Eq. 10) species
499 over strontium and barium sites at the catalyst surface (where M represents Sr or Ba ions).
500 Hence, the NO_x adsorption mechanism is similar to the reported for NSR model catalyst [56,
501 57],

502 Among the developed formulations, Ba-doped samples show the lowest NO_x outlet
503 concentration.

504

FIGURE 12

505 After 150 s of the lean period, oxygen is cut off and replaced by hydrogen which reacts with
506 stored NO_x to form NH₃, N₂O and N₂. The developed formulations produce different nitrogen
507 containing species, as a result of an efficient NO_x reduction during rich conditions. Regarding
508 NH₃ and N₂O, similar maximum outlet concentration can be observed in all cases, with values
509 around 300–400 ppm and 200–250 ppm, respectively. Meanwhile, Ba-doped samples show
510 slightly higher N₂ signals. According to literature, the reduction of the stored nitrates with
511 hydrogen could follow the following reactions (Eqs. 11–13) during the rich period [58, 59]:

512 It is widely accepted [60, 61] that at high temperatures N_2 formation is promoted due to reaction
 513 of the NH_3 formed with stored nitrates downstream to form N_2 (Equation 14),

514 The proposed mechanism consists of a sequential two-step pathway for nitrogen formation
 515 involving the fast formation of NH_3 on reaction of nitrates with H_2 , followed by the slower
 516 reaction of the NH_3 formed with the stored nitrates leading to the selective formation of N_2
 517 (Figure 12). In agreement with this reaction pathway, the NH_3 signal is delayed with respect to
 518 N_2O and N_2 signals in all cases. It is worth to mention that a fraction of the NO_x stored is
 519 released without being converted in all cases, which denotes faster nitrates decomposition than
 520 NO_x reduction [13]. However, NO_x released extent strongly depends on perovskite formulation.
 521 Ba-doped samples show the lowest NO_x outlet concentration during rich conditions. It could be
 522 attributed, first of all, to the stronger bonding of adsorbed NO_x species to the Ba-doped samples
 523 (Fig. 9, NO_x -TPD experiments). Furthermore, the higher interaction between Pd and perovskite
 524 observed by H_2 -TPR experiments enables a better diffusion of the H_2 from the Pd to the
 525 perovskite active sites, promoting NO_x reduction capacity for Ba-doped samples.

526 Figure 13a shows the evolution of NO_x storage capacity (*NSC*) with reaction temperature for the
 527 developed formulations. As a general trend, all samples show a volcano-type dependence of the
 528 *NSC* on the temperature with a maximum performance around 350–400 °C [3, 62]. Below
 529 350 °C, NO_x adsorption capacities increase due to nitrate route promotion, as a consequence of
 530 the higher NO_2 concentrations, in good agreement with the results observed on Fig. 11. At
 531 higher temperatures, the *NSC* decreased probably due to the lower nitrites/nitrates stability
 532 together with the decreased NO oxidation capacity.

533 As previously discussed in Figures 8–10, the perovskite composition influences *NSC* during
 534 lean period. Among the prepared catalysts, Ba-doped samples showed the best performance
 535 with maximum *NSC* ~ 90% (300-400 °C), whereas the maximum *NSC* for Pd–
 536 LSCO (0.3)/ Al_2O_3 is below 74%. The higher *NSC* below 300 °C is ascribed to a more
 537 homogeneous distribution of Pd and perovskite phases, which explains the lower differences
 538 between the developed samples. In contrast, as many works have already reported [44, 63], *NSC*

539 increases proportionally with surface basicity at high temperatures. In order to confirm the
540 relation between both parameters, Figure 13b shows the *NSC* at 350 °C as a function of surface
541 basicity. As can be observed, there exists a linear relation between both parameters, in good
542 agreement with the highest *NSC* of Pd–LBCO(0.5)/Al₂O₃ catalyst. Nonetheless, it is worth to
543 mention that Ba-doped formulations show similar *NSC* below 350 °C. This trend is due to the
544 similar weak and medium basicity of both formulations, as reported in Table 4. Thus, the higher
545 *NSC* for Pd–LBCO (0.5)/Al₂O₃ above this temperature is due to the higher concentration of
546 strong basic sites. Based on these results, it seems that the gas/solid equilibrium between NO₂
547 and the available NO_x adsorption sites is the key factor to maximize the *NSC* [14, 63]. Taking
548 into account that NO–to–NO₂ conversions are high in all cases in Figure 11, the improvement of
549 the *NSC* is mainly ascribed to an increase in the concentration of NO_x adsorption sites at the
550 surface, as quantified in Table 4.

551

FIGURE 13

552 Figure 14 shows the NO global conversion (X_{NO}) and different products distribution at 150,
553 250, 350 and 450 °C for the fully formulated samples. As a general trend, NO global conversion
554 shows a similar dependence with temperature than the *NSC* (Figure 13a). In fact, the differences
555 between Sr and Ba-doped formulations are proportional to those observed in *NSC*. Hence, Ba-
556 doped samples show the highest NO global conversion (maximum around 90%). This trend is
557 mainly ascribed to the higher amount of NO_x stored during lean period, which implies higher
558 amount of NO_x available to be reduced during the subsequent rich period [13]. This fact was
559 further evidenced by the proportional decrease of NO₂ production (Y_{NO_2}) observed in Figure 14
560 for the samples with higher *NSC*, which is mainly ascribed to the NO₂ non-adsorbed during lean
561 conditions. However, these catalysts have to reduce efficiently the adsorbed nitrates/nitrites
562 during short rich period. This path can be promoted by higher Pd–perovskite interactions and
563 slower NO_x release. As previously observed by H₂–TPR experiments (Fig. 6), Ba-doped
564 samples exhibited a closer contact between Pd and perovskite phases. As a result, the reduction
565 of N_xO_y species adsorbed over Ba-containing sites by Pd in close contact is significantly
566 promoted [64, 65]. Furthermore, Ba-doped samples also showed the highest strength of NO_x
567 adsorbed species by NO_x–TPD experiments (Figure 9). Hence, a higher amount of NO_x stored
568 can be reduced during the subsequent rich period. In order to verify this statement, Figure S5
569 plots the evolution of NO_x conversion during rich period with reaction temperature for Sr and
570 Ba-doped samples. As can be observed, all samples show excellent NO_x reduction capacity,
571 especially at low and intermediate temperatures. Meanwhile, above 350 °C, the faster nitrates
572 decomposition limits progressively NO_x reduction. Among fully formulated samples, the Pd–
573 LBCO (0.5)/Al₂O₃ catalyst shows the best NO_x conversion during rich period, especially at high

574 temperatures in line with its higher basicity. Thus, NO_x storage capacity and the adsorbed
575 nitrites/nitrates stability can be considered as the key factors for NO_x reduction during rich
576 period.

577 **FIGURE 14**

578 As a final step, the NO_x should be selectively reduced to N₂. In agreement with NSC and X_{NO},
579 the maximum nitrogen production is obtained at 350 °C (Figure 14). Ba-based catalysts show
580 the highest nitrogen yield (Y_{N₂}). Indeed, the maximum Y_{N₂} ranges from 72% for Pd–
581 LBCO(0.5)/Al₂O₃ sample to 56% for Pd–LSCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃.

582 Figure 14 also includes the NO₂, N₂O and NH₃ productions at the analyzed temperature levels.
583 Regarding ammonia production, all samples show the maximum values (19-24%) at 150–
584 200 °C, decreasing gradually at higher reaction temperatures. It has been already reported [56,
585 62], that NH₃ production (Y_{NH₃}) at low temperatures is promoted with high H₂–to–stored nitrates
586 ratio. Meanwhile, at higher temperatures, the improvement of NO_x adsorption results in a nearly
587 total hydrogen consumption. Hence, the NH₃ formed in the initial part of the catalysts reacts
588 with stored nitrates downstream to form N₂ (Equation 14). As previously observed in Figure 12,
589 this leads to a delay of the ammonia breakthrough with respect to N₂ and N₂O one. Moreover,
590 N₂ could also be produced by the NH₃ partial oxidation with O₂ stored over perovskite. As a
591 consequence the reductant–to–stored NO_x ratio decreases. These facts explain the decrease of
592 ammonia production above 200 °C.

593 Regarding NO₂ production, it progressively increases from zero value to a maximum of around
594 12–20% at 450 °C. This trend is ascribed to a progressive promotion of NO–to–NO₂ conversion
595 (Figure 11) together to the progressive decrease of nitrates stability. The later point explains the
596 lowest NO₂ production for the sample with the highest surface basicity (Pd–LBCO(0.5)/Al₂O₃).
597 Finally, the N₂O production (Y_{N₂O}) values are below 6% regardless the temperature and the
598 formulation. This confirms the weak capability of these formulations for NO dissociation to
599 form N₂O [41, 66].

600 In summary, Ba-doped samples show the best balance between NO–to–NO₂ oxidation capacity,
601 and NO_x adsorption sites concentration and strength at the surface. As a result, the NO_x storage
602 capacity is significantly promoted. Furthermore, the La partial substitution by Ba slows down
603 the NO_x release during rich conditions due to the higher strength of adsorbed species. Thus, NO_x
604 reduction and as a consequence nitrogen yield are enhanced for this type of formulations. In this
605 sense, the La_{0.5}Ba_{0.5}CoO₃-based catalyst is set as the optimum formulation for NO_x removal by
606 NSR technology. The great impact of the results obtained in this study was confirmed by the

607 comparison made in Figure S6. As a general trend, Pd–LBCO(0.5)/Al₂O₃ alternative shows
608 significantly higher DeNO_x activity than Pt-based model formulation (1.5 wt.% Pt–
609 15 wt.% Ba/Al₂O₃) under same reaction conditions, this fact remarks the applicability of the
610 developed formulation for NO_x removal in diesel engines.

611 4. CONCLUSIONS

612 The modification of the perovskite composition affects the surface properties of the Pd–
613 30% La_{1-x}AB_xO₃/Al₂O₃-type catalysts. In particular, the following perovskite formulations
614 (ABO₃) were selected: La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃ perovskite, as the optimum formulation set in our
615 previous work, as well as La_{0.7}Ba_{0.3}CoO₃ and La_{0.5}Ba_{0.5}CoO₃ perovskites as alternative
616 formulations. Interestingly, XRD and Raman experiments reveal that perovskite purity and the
617 different phase's distribution depend on perovskite composition. On the one hand, the amount
618 of impurities in form of BaCO₃ and BaCoO_{2.95} is higher for Ba-doped samples. On the other
619 hand, these formulations favor a more homogeneous distribution of Co₃O₄, BaCO₃ and PdO
620 phases. As result, interactions between Pd and perovskite can be also strengthened. This fact
621 together with the higher intrinsic basicity of Ba than Sr led to a progressive increase of the
622 surface basicity from 14.6 μmol CO₂ g⁻¹ for 1.9 wt.% Pd–30 wt.% La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃/Al₂O₃ catalyst,
623 to 25.5 μmol CO₂ g⁻¹ for 1.9 wt.% Pd–30 wt.% La_{0.5}Ba_{0.5}CoO₃/Al₂O₃ catalyst (CO₂–TPD). The
624 basicity of these samples governs the decomposition temperature of these surface nitrate
625 species. The more basic is the adsorbent, stronger the bonding to the surface. As a result, the
626 amount as well as the strength of the NO_x adsorbed species is higher for 1.9 wt.% Pd–
627 30 wt.% La_{0.5}Ba_{0.5}CoO₃/Al₂O₃ catalyst, as observed by NO_x–TPD experiments.

628 Among the prepared catalysts, 1.9 wt.% Pd–30 wt.%La_{0.5}Ba_{0.5}CoO₃/Al₂O₃ exhibits the highest
629 NO_x storage capacity in the NO_x storage and reduction experiments, with a maximum around
630 90%. Since similar NO oxidation capacities were reported irrespectively the perovskite phase
631 composition, the observed differences are related to the concentration and strength of the NO_x
632 adsorption sites at the surface. Indeed, a linear relation between NSC and surface basicity was
633 confirmed for this type of formulations. These results unequivocally reveal that the
634 concentration of NO_x adsorption sites is directly related to surface basicity, which in turn gives
635 an idea of the concentration and distribution of the segregations in form of Ba or Sr-based
636 phases.

637 The global NO_x conversion and nitrogen production values follow a similar trend to the one
638 reported for NO_x storage capacity. As a result, 1.9 wt.% Pd–30 wt.% La_{0.5}Ba_{0.5}CoO₃/Al₂O₃
639 shows the highest values, 90% and 72%, respectively. However, the observed differences were
640 higher to the reported for NO_x storage capacity. This trend was assigned to the higher strength

641 of the NO_x adsorbed species as well as the closer contact between Pd and perovskite sites which
642 promoted the NO_x adsorbed species reduction. This designed material achieves superior
643 catalytic performances than those of the reference 1.9 wt.% Pd–30 wt.% La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃/Al₂O₃,
644 previously developed, and Pt-based model formulation. Thus, this catalyst can be considered a
645 promising alternative to conventional Pt–Ba/Al₂O₃ for NO_x emission control in diesel engines.

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765

766 **FIGURES CAPTIONS**

767 **Graphical abstract.**

768 Reaction mechanism during NO_x storage and reduction process (lean-rich periods).

769

770 **Table 1.** Textural properties of the fully formulated samples, together with those of the
771 support as reference.

772 **Table 2.** Pd weight contents and dispersion, Pd 3d_{5/2} BE position and atomic content
773 obtained for the fully formulated samples together with Pd/Al₂O₃ reference sample.

774 **Table 3.** Deconvoluted hydrogen consumption related to different reduction steps for
775 supported perovskites with increasing palladium incorporated by impregnation or
776 by doping together with Pd/Al₂O₃ reference sample.

777 **Table 4.** Deconvoluted CO₂ desorption related to different basic sites strength for the fully
778 formulated samples.

779

780 **Figure 1.** a) XRD diffractograms of the fully formulated samples, bulk La_{0.5}Ba_{0.5}CoO₃
781 (LBCO(0.5)) and La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃ (LSCO(0.3)) perovskites and Al₂O₃ support; and
782 b) enlargement of the specific zone from 32 to 35° 2θ for developed formulations
783 together with bulk LaCoO₃ perovskite (LSCO(0)). ♣ Al₂O₃, ▲ SrCO₃, ● BaCoO_{2.95}
784 and ◆ BaCO₃.

785 **Figure 2.** Raman spectra of the specific zones: a) 250-750 cm⁻¹ and b) 850-1350 cm⁻¹ for Pd-
786 LSCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃, Pd-LBCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ and Pd-LBCO(0.5)/Al₂O₃ samples.

787 **Figure 3.** Raman images plotting the intensity of the bands at 690 cm⁻¹ (Co₃O₄), 645 cm⁻¹
788 (PdO) and 1057 or 1070 cm⁻¹ (BaCO₃ or SrCO₃), for Pd-LSCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ (left
789 column) and Pd-30% LBCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ (right column) samples.

790 **Figure 4.** STEM images and the corresponding EDX analysis mapping of Pd, La, Al, Co and
791 Sr or Ba for Pd-LSCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ and Pd-LBCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ catalysts. Pd
792 nanoparticles marked with yellow arrows.

793 **Figure 5.** XPS spectra of Pd 3d of the fully formulated samples together with Pd/Al₂O₃
794 reference sample.

795 **Figure 6.** H₂-TPR profiles normalized per mass unit of different supported perovskites;
796 previously (a) and after (b) palladium incorporation.

797 **Figure 7.** CO₂-desorption profiles normalized according to sample mass for: a) Pd-
798 LBCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ throughout the different preparation steps, and b) fully
799 formulated samples.

800 **Figure 8.** NO_x desorption profiles of: a) Al₂O₃ support, b) Pd/Al₂O₃, c) LBCO(0.5)/Al₂O₃
801 and d) Pd-LBCO(0.5)/Al₂O₃ samples.

802 **Figure 9.** NO_x desorption profiles of: a) Pd-LSCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃, b) Pd-LBCO(0.3)/Al₂O₃ and
803 c) Pd-LBCO(0.5)/Al₂O₃ samples.

804 **Figure 10.** Deconvoluted total NO_x desorption of: a) Pd-LBCO(0.5)/Al₂O₃ variant throughout
805 different preparation steps and b) fully formulated samples.

806 **Figure 11.** Evolution of NO-to-NO₂ conversion ($X_{NO-to-NO_2}$) capacity with temperature for
807 fully formulated samples.

808 **Figure 12.** NO_x (NO+NO₂), NH₃, N₂O and N₂ outlet concentrations during two consecutive
809 lean-rich cycles in stationary state of fully formulated samples at 350 °C (Note
810 different scale for concentration of each component).

811 **Figure 13.** Evolution of: a) NO_x storage capacity (NSC) with reaction temperature; and b) NO_x
812 storage capacity at $350\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, as a function of the surface basicity for the different
813 developed formulations.

814 **Figure 14.** Global conversion of NO (X_{NO}) and products distribution at 150, 250, 350 and
815 $450\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for developed formulations.

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Table 1.
Textural properties of the fully formulated samples, together with those of the support as reference.

Sample	$S_{\text{BET}}, \text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$	$V_p, \text{cm}^3 \text{g}^{-1}$	d_c, nm^*
$\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$	186.5	0.63	—
Pd-LSCO(0.3)/Al ₂ O ₃	119.1	0.37	13 (18)
Pd-LBCO(0.3)/Al ₂ O ₃	122.7	0.39	14 (21)
Pd-LBCO(0.5)/Al ₂ O ₃	121.0	0.37	16 (18)

821 * The values in brackets correspond to the crystal size of the corresponding bulk counterpart.

822

823

Table 2.

824 Pd weight contents and dispersion ($\text{Pd}_{\text{disp.}}$), Pd $3d_{5/2}$ BE position and atomic content obtained for
 825 the fully formulated samples together with Pd/ Al_2O_3 reference sample.

Sample	Pd, wt. %	$\text{Pd}_{\text{disp.}}$, %	Pd $3d_{5/2}$, eV	Surface Pd concentration (atomic %) ^a
Pd-LSCO(0.3)/ Al_2O_3	1.9	19.4	336.2	0.5
Pd-LBCO(0.3)/ Al_2O_3	1.9	24.0	337.1	0.5
Pd-LBCO(0.5)/ Al_2O_3	1.9	22.2	336.6	0.5
Pd/ Al_2O_3	1.9	26.3	336.1	---

826 ^a Integration of the peak of the Pd $3d_{5/2}$ spectra from the XPS analysis.

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828

Table 3.

829

Deconvoluted hydrogen consumption related to different reduction steps for fully formulated

830

samples together with Pd/Al₂O₃ reference sample.

Sample	PdO→Pd ⁰ ^(a) , μmol H ₂ g ⁻¹	PdO–Co ^(b) , μmol H ₂ g ⁻¹	Co ⁺³ →Co ⁰ ^(c) , μmol H ₂ g ⁻¹	CoAl ₂ O ₄ ^(d) , μmol H ₂ g ⁻¹	H ₂ /Pd ^(e)
Pd–LSCO (0.3)/Al ₂ O ₃	82	415	303	1150	0.53
Pd–LBCO (0.3)/Al ₂ O ₃	13	446	239	1124	0.09
Pd–LBCO (0.5)/Al ₂ O ₃	11	572	285	1221	0.07
Pd/Al ₂ O ₃	152	---	---	---	0.99

831

^(a) Integration of peak centered around 30 °C.

832

^(b) Integrated peak centered around 125–200 °C.

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^(c) Integrated peak centered around 300–350 °C.

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^(d) Sum of integrated peaks above 600 °C, assigned to cobalt aluminate reduction and corresponding carbonates decomposition.

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836

^(e) Hydrogen consumption in the first peak related to Pd content in the sample.

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Table 4.

840 Deconvoluted CO₂ desorption related to different basic sites strength for the fully formulated
841 samples.

Sample	$\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ ($< 550 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$)	$\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ ($> 550 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$)	$\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ (Total)
Pd-LSCO (0.3)/Al ₂ O ₃	14.6	6.5	21.1
Pd-LBCO (0.3)/Al ₂ O ₃	19.6	4.5	24.1
Pd-LBCO (0.5)/Al ₂ O ₃	19.8	5.6	25.5

842

Figure 1
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Figure 11_R1
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Figure 12

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Figure 13

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Lean period

Rich period

Highlights

- NO_x removal efficiency of Pd– $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{A}_x\text{CoO}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ -type catalysts is analyzed.
- The modification of perovskite surface composition by Ba-doping favors NO_x adsorption and reduction.
- 1.9% Pd-30% $\text{La}_{0.5}\text{Ba}_{0.5}\text{CoO}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ shows maximum N_2 yield of 72.0%.
- Maximum NO_x removal efficiency is due to higher accessibility and strength of NO_x adsorption sites.
- Promising formulations as base material for automotive catalysts.

Supplementary Material

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